
SOCIAL MEDIA TOOLS AND LIBRARY SERVICE

Mr. Narayan Hemaji Mengal

Librarian,

Rayat Shikshan Sanstha's, Swami Sahajanand Bharati College of Education, Shirampur.

Corresponding Author - Mr. Narayan Hemaji Mengal

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Abstract:

The developments in Web technology are creating more friendly, social, and fun environments for retrieving and sharing information and one of such is social media networking websites. However, it has been observed that despite the promise of social networking sites, limited libraries are adopting them for rendering services to their patrons and this consequently results in limited patronage and response from the users. The vast growth of knowledge and literature in every field of education along with the advancement of information technology has placed special responsibilities on all types of libraries. Nowadays, different types of social media tools are increasingly used in library works in academic libraries. Librarians, in this digital age, are responsible for a wide variety of resources and services that expand far beyond the typical eight-hour work day. Promotion in library and information science has a newer meaning. It finds deep roots in social media. It is a set of techniques which is aimed at reinforcing the basic values of the library in a changing environment at the same time meeting the needs of the library clientele. Essentially, promotion is the means of informing users on what you do and what you can do.

Key Words: *Social Media Tools, Library Service, Information Technology.*

Introduction:

During the last 20 years, technology became a major factor on the library scenario. There have been several developments in information technology which may be characterized as revolutionary in terms of their actual or potential effect on the library. The term 'Social media' is described in different ways and for different functions. Social media are mainly internet-based tools for sharing, distributing and discussing information among the people. Social media refers to web-based tools that help individuals and organizations to generate, attach, share information and communicate

with the people. In the era of internet social media applications became very powerful tool for all types of libraries. The range of social media application in the library include communication with users, library services, user education, creating awareness of library resources, communicate other librarians and staffs, getting opinion or feedback from the users and staffs etc. Social media are used in academic libraries in different purposes, mainly in information communication, information sharing and knowledge organization. Mainly, , Facebook, Twitter, Instagram, Twitter, Telegram, Blog and money more etc., are used for information

communication and Flickr, YouTube, Wikipedia, Slideshare etc. are used for information sharing and Library thing etc., are used for knowledge organization. In the present era, the librarian can keep contact with the library users and staffs in online collaborative environment with the help of social media.

Social Network:

Social network is a website that brings people together to talk, share ideas and interests, or make new friends. This type of collaboration and sharing of data is often referred to as social media. Unlike traditional media that is often created by limited people only, social media sites contain content that has been created by hundreds or even millions of different people.

Role of Social Networking Tool in Libraries:

Social media tools play a vital role in every domain especially with Library and information Science. Google generation users are nowadays able to get the required information through their hand held devices. This is the challenging environment for the libraries and library professionals to carry the right information to the user community in this emerging technology based platforms. Academic Libraries can also respond to the needs of modern day patrons by applying modern technologies such as social networking, mobile application, and online check in/check outs to their service delivery. Social Networks can be used for providing user centric service in academic library environment. User attitude towards library is changing day by day. User expect from libraries most practical and speed information in technological age. But providing quick and easy retrieval

information to user is a great challenge to library professionals. Therefore library professionals should find and search some new techniques for impacting valuable information to the end user. The impact of social networking sites in libraries is growing day by day. Many libraries are using social networking platform to interact and reach out to their patrons or clients.

Nowadays LIS professionals have started adapting themselves to the popularity of social networking sites and their expanding role in the creation, exploitation, and sharing of information by engaging them as a central medium for interacting with library users and providing services to meet their information needs. Information Technology literate librarian is capable of teaching these skills to library users. This includes guiding and training of users through social networking sites that are used as resources and tools for teaching, learning and research purposes. Academic LIS Professionals possessing these skills are capable of efficient and effective navigation of online social networking sites and applying their expertise to services with and within the social networking platforms.

Objectives of using Social Media tools in Libraries:

- Librarians can tweet about events of daily activities in the library.
- To know update of new books, journals and other and new arrivals in library members of interest.
- The Using instant messenger apps also library staff can send alert messages to the library patrons for discharge of books and fine reminder

- The youtube channel for the library and host events and live Programmes taking place in the library.
- Sharing library programmes photos using with photo sharing tools like as flickr, pinterest.
- Create a library patron groups for sharing information by using tools like WhatsApp, Telegram.
- To share the public or private messages related to the library and its services
- To create groups between the library and users to discuss the new age of information or services.

Most Popular Networking Tools for Library:

- **Facebook** is a very handy and easy social media platform that is being used by all academic librarians and users. Facebook allows us to form groups of like-minded persons having common needs. All users can freely communicate with everyone on the group so formed for library services.
- **Twitter** is a micro blogging application. It will keep up staff and users updated on daily activities, like regularly updated collections, new arrival, current content services of library.
- **WhatsApp** is an internationally available freeware, cross-platform centralized instant messaging (IM) and voice-over-IP (VoIP) service owned by American company Meta Platforms (formerly Facebook). It allows users to send text and voice messages, make voice and video calls, and share images, documents, user locations, and other content.

- **Telegram** is a globally accessible free, cross-platform, cloud-based instant messaging (IM) service. The service also provides optional end-to-end encrypted chats and video calling, VoIP, file sharing and several other features.
- **LinkedIn:** This social networking site for professionals is a great way to get library users connected with the people that can help them find information.
- **Blog:** Many aspiring as well as established authors, journalist and celebrities are using blogs to write their views and ideas. Through blogging librarians can inform users about the availability of new collections and being in contact with the users and their needs.
- **YouTube:** This is the most popular social media site for teaching learning videos, e-learning tutorials, and related events.
- **Wikipedia:** This is an online encyclopedia updated by users. You can use this tool to share your knowledge by editing, or simply point library users in the right direction.
- **Slide Share:** Encourage faculty, staff, and students to share their slideshow presentations for the greater community to access on Slide Share. It is a great way to disseminate information among research community to the field of research and development activities.
- **Library Thing:** This social cataloging network site for librarians and you can catalogue along with Amazon, the Library of Congress, and more than 300 other libraries around the world. You

will get recommendations and easy tagging as well.

Benefits of Social Media tools in Libraries:

- Access to easy, instant communication tools.
- Chance to connect with people around the world.
- It helps people who are shy or socially isolated to connect with others
- An immediate access to their teaching updates.
- Refines strategies.
- Improves innovation and learning.
- It develops communicative skills along with social rapport
- It allows users to quickly share their academic tasks.

Some of the Disadvantages for Social Media Tools:

- Inadequate library staff.
- Slow speed of Internet.
- Lack of knowledge how to use it.
- Inadequate training opportunities for library staff.
- Too many social media tools to learn Lack of privacy and identity theft.
- Confidentiality of information.
- Electricity failure.

Conclusion:

The people using the social media in India will increase day by day. In the current social media tools have become important communication tools for attract everyone with its unique features of update information. The social media users can share their ideas, feelings, images, documents, videos, with others through social media tools like as Whats app, facebook, twitter and etc. This tool can

conveys library services though the social media. Social media is being used more and more in educational libraries today. Almost all libraries have started using social media tools to promote their services and resources, which is also considered to be an effective platform for in-house professional communication in any institutions. The social media tools are considered to be a useful base to introduce library services through web technology for the benefit of both the Library and Information Science professional and to the library users. The ultimate ideology of using social media tools is to promote library services and resources and to improve the prominence of the library.

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